

STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING ENGLISH APHORISMS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. Aphorism is one of the common linguistic phenomena and a challenge a translator may encounter. This article is devoted to the problems arising in the translation of aphorisms and their solutions, reflecting that when translating aphorisms, the main content and essence in them should not lose their clarity. Due to the structural differences of aphoristic expressions between the English and Uzbek languages as well as the different images between the two languages which may have an impact on the process of translation and consequently bring about some problems in finding suitable and appropriate equivalences from English into Uzbek.

Keywords: translation of aphorisms, equivalence, lexical, syntactic, zero transformation, replacement of parts of speech, omission, addition, modulation.

Annotatsiya. Aforizm-bu keng tarqalgan lingvistik hodisalardan biri bo'lib, uning tarjimasini jarayonida tarjimon bir qator qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola aforizmlarni tarjima qilishda yuzaga keladigan muammolar va ularning yechimlariga qaratilgan bo'lib, aforizmlarni tarjima qilishda, ulardagi asosiy mazmun va mohiyat o'z softligini yo'qotmasligi lozimligi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari o'rtasidagi aforizmlarning tarkibiy farqlari hamda ikki til o'rtasidagi turli xil qarashlar tufayli tarjima jarayoniga ta'sir ko'rsatishi va natijada ingliz tilidan o'zbek tiliga mos ekvivalentlarni topishda ba'zi muammolarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: aforizmlar tarjimasini, ekvivalentlik, leksik, sintaktik, so'zma-so'z tarjima, so'z turkumlarini almashtirish, tushirib qoldirish, qo'shish, modulyatsiya.

Açıklama. Aforizma yaygın dilsel olgulardan biridir, çevirisi sürecinde çevirmen bir dizi zorlukla karşılaşabilir. Bu makale, aforizmaların çevirisinde karşılaşılan sorunlara ve bunların çözümlerine odaklanmakta, aforizmaları çevirirken ana içeriğin ve özün netliğini kaybetmemesi gerektiğini yansıtmaktadır. İngilizce ve Özbekçe arasındaki aforizmalarda yapısal farklılıkların yanı sıra iki dil arasındaki farklı görüşler nedeniyle çeviri sürecini etkileyebilir ve sonuç olarak İngilizceden Özbekçeye uygun karşılıkların bulunmasında bazı sorunlara neden olabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: aforizma çevirisi, eşdeğerlik, sözcüksel, sözdizimsel, birebir çeviri, sözcük kategorilerinin değiştirilmesi, çıkarma, ekleme, modülasyon.

Аннотация. Афоризм-одно из распространенных языковых явлений, в процессе перевода которого переводчик может столкнуться с рядом трудностей. Данная статья посвящена проблемам, возникающим при переводе афоризмов, и их решениям, отражающим то, что при переводе афоризмов основное содержание и суть в них не должны терять свою ясность. Из-за структурных различий в афористических выражениях между английским и узбекским языками, а также различных образов между двумя языками, которые могут оказать влияние на процесс перевода и, следовательно, вызвать некоторые проблемы с поиском подходящих эквивалентов с английского на узбекский.

Ключевые слова: перевод афоризмов, эквивалентность, лексический, синтаксический, нулевая трансформация, замена частей речи, опущение, дополнение, модуляция.

Translation is a complex and multifaceted type of human activity, that has accompanied humankind throughout its history, at least since the emergence of primitive languages and culture. Different theorists state numerous definitions for translation. Newmark defines translation as the endeavor to replace a written message and/or statement in one language with the same message and/or statement in another language. Catford points out that translation is the process of replacing textual material in one language (SL) with textual material in another language. According to S. Ojegov translation is a text translated from one language into another. Winter noted that to translate means to replace the formulation of the interpretation of a segment of the world around us with another, if possible equivalent, formulation.

These and many other definitions take on a completely different meaning when we stop considering translation, as a purely linguistic phenomenon. Translators may run across challenges or difficulties throughout the translating process. "Mistakes, misjudgments, miscalculations, and error comprise an integral element of learning in obtaining knowledge," writes Brown.

Miremadi divides translation problems into two categories: lexical and syntactic issues. Lexical meaning refers to words or phrases that appear to be equal but are not; the translator must be aware of the author's intent beyond the words to avoid misrepresenting the author's message. Miremadi noted that no two languages have the same structural organization systems (i.e., language structure varies from one language to another). These distinctions include word classes, grammatical relations, word order, style, and pragmatic aspects.

Translation requires such a deep understanding of the text that the work acquires the character of the original written in the target language. On the other hand, translation requires strict adherence to the stylistic peculiarities of the original language, i.e. preservation of neutral vocabulary, high style, clericalisms, etc. in the translation in the right places. The object of this research is the study of the problems of translating English aphorisms into Uzbek and the difficulties faced by the translator of aphorisms.

Aphorisms have always been popular among people, but lately they have become especially relevant. This interest can be explained the fact that the peculiarities of the modern era require concise ways of expressing thought. There is also an increased research interest in the problems of aphorisms, reflected in an increase in the number of scientific publications devoted to their study. Despite the fact that aphorism has existed since ancient times, it does not have a proper theoretical description: existing scientific knowledge and its boundaries are very vague. There is no well-developed and well-founded theory of aphoristics in the world literature, which gives rise to many ambiguities in modern science. Despite the rather active interest of researchers in aphorisms, at the present stage they have not been studied to the proper extent: there is no generally recognized definition and classifications, characteristics and functions have not been identified. All these issues remain highly debatable.

In the theory and practice of translation, an aphorism is regarded as a small artistic work, not as a repetitive unity of concise expression of thought. Therefore, aphorisms can be considered completely independent units of language and can be studied independently. Aphorisms express the speaker's thought not only more specifically, but also meaningfully, figuratively, and most importantly - emotionally. Linguistic aphorisms are used by the speaker to consolidate his opinion, conviction in his word. In other words, aphorisms are used to decorate speech, to make it more colourful.

The translation of aphorisms as part of a literary text or as a kind of complete work belongs to literary translation, which is, perhaps, the most difficult field in translation studies because in

such work the translator does not only translate, and in a certain way writes a new text in the language of the translation. In the process of translating information, the translator looks for the necessary meaning of a word among all possible ones, if this word is polysemantic. The content of the word is not autonomous; it depends on the context, so the translator must be able to analyze the context. Sometimes it is necessary to go to the level of a word combination or sentence, and sometimes it is necessary to read the entire text to understand all the nuances and meanings of unfamiliar words. Therefore, translation work requires patience, language skills and extensive education.

When translating aphorisms, as well as any other text, it is necessary to observe the norms of equivalence, i.e., to preserve the relative equality of the substantive, semantic, stylistic and communicative information contained in the texts of the original and the translation. Equivalence is one of the most important conditions for the existence of translation and is considered a central concept in translation theory.

A.V. Fedorov emphasizes that when translating aphorisms, it is necessary to select lively variants close to the colloquial style in order to avoid excessive bookish prudery, and preference should also be given to the concrete material form of expression.

Aphorisms of George Bernard Shaw were used as material for the study. The analysis involved a translation made by Odam Valiev.

A Nobel laureate, George Bernard Shaw was an Irish playwright who exerted an indomitable influence on Western culture, theatre and politics with his write-ups. Shaw's writing style was arch different from what was practiced in those days. He introduced realism into playwriting by using the platform to stage his political, social and religious ideas. Shaw's writing style was unique. He is acknowledged as the writer who most nearly approaches Shakespeare in his mastery of the craft of drama. The prefaces to his plays reveal that he was also a brilliant essayist and one of the great aphorists of the century.

When translating aphorisms from English to Uzbek, the following techniques can be used: *zero transformation, replacement of parts of speech, omission, addition, change of sentence type, generalization, concretization, noun number replacement, antonymic translation, verb tense category replacement, passive construction replacement with active construction and vice versa, modulation, segmentation and combining of sentences.*

The translation of aphorisms belongs to literary translation, therefore, work with the texts of this genre is quite difficult. Since a literal translation is impossible, because it distorts the meaning of the expression or loses it altogether, the translator must resort to certain transformations, with the help of which the text of the translation language will be semantically maximal only close to the text of the original language.

As a result of the analysis, the following translation transformations were found:

Zero transformation

Activity is the only road to knowledge. - Faoliyat – bilimga yagona yo'l.

Imagination is the beginning of creation. - Tasavvur ijodning boshlanishidir.

In these examples, we see the complete preservation of syntactic constructions in translation, the words are taken in their direct meaning, therefore, zero transformation is applied.

Replacement of parts of speech

Perhaps the greatest social service that can be rendered by anybody to the country and to mankind is to bring up a family.- Odam mamlakat va insoniyat uchun qilishi mumkin bo'lgan eng katta xizmat – bolalarini tarbiyalashidir.

In translation, the pronoun "anybody" is transferred to the noun "odam".

Omission

The liar's punishment is not in the least that he is not believed, but that he cannot believe anyone else. - Yolg'onchiga berilgan jazo unga boshqalar ishonmay qo'ygani emas, u boshqalarga ortiq ishona olmasligidir.

The translation omits the superlative adjective "the least". The conjunction "but" was omitted in the translation.

Addition

Both optimists and pessimists contribute to society. The optimist invents the aeroplane, the pessimist the parachute. - Jamiyatga optimistlar ham, pessimistlar ham hissa qo'shadi. Optimist samolyotni o'ylab topgan bo'lsa, pessimist parashyutni ixtiro qilgan.

In Uzbek translation the verb "ixtiro qilgan" is added to the second part of the sentence, though there is no verb in English version.

Modulation

The test of a man or woman's breeding is how they behave in a quarrel. -Erkak yoki ayolning tarbiyalanganlik darajasi janjal paytida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.

The meaning of the word "test" has been modulated, since the meaning in the dictionary of this word is an examination of somebody's knowledge or ability, consisting of questions.

Practical recommendations for the translation of aphorisms.

1. Analyze the statement, identify its meaning, the main meaning and intentions of the author (what the author wanted to say with this statement.)
2. Study the structure of the statement.
3. Analyze the aphorism for the use of translation techniques.
4. During the application of various translation transformations, take into account the grammatical and lexical features of the language into which the aphorism is translated.
5. It is necessary to observe the idiomatic style of utterance.
6. When translating, keep the form of the aphorism.
7. Try to bring the translation closer to the literal one.
8. In the above statement, check for the presence of elements of the meaning of all the thoughts and intentions of the author.

When translating an aphorism, the translator should convey the meaning of what was said as accurately as possible and try to preserve the form of the statement. Since Uzbek is a synthetic language and English is an analytical language, words in English require not only translation but also clarification in Uzbek. If the translator has special difficulties in translating a particular expression or word, it is possible to resort to descriptive translation. Thus, we believe that this topic represents a wide area for further research, as the aphorism is an interesting and rather complex translation problem, moreover, not fully studied, which the translator must take into account in order to create an equivalent in content and equal in value literary work in the target language.

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